

Kartagener's Syndrome With Infantile Spasms

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INTRODUCTION

Kartagener's syndrome is an autosomal recessive disorder. It is a subset of primary ciliary dyskinesia that is characterized by situs inversus totalis (mirror-image reversal of internal organs) [1]. The signs and symptoms include respiratory distress in neonates, frequent infections of lung, sinus, and middle ear starting in early childhood, chronic nasal congestion, hydrocephalus, and infertility [1]. Its incidence is about 1 in 30,000 live births. Because of immotile spermatozoa, male patients with this syndrome are almost always infertile [2]. The diagnosis is quite often delayed until late childhood or adulthood because of the disease's diversity, paucity of physician knowledge of disease characteristics, and the technical expertise required for making a correct diagnosis of primary ciliary dyskinesia. Primary ciliary dyskinesia should be considered in the differential diagnosis of several clinical presentations, like unexplained respiratory distress and/or laterality defect, chronic cough, nasal drainage, and sino-pulmonary disease in infants and children.

CASE HISTORY

A 27 months old male baby presented to the outpatient department with complaints of abnormal body movements (myoclonic jerks) 6 months after birth, recurrent episodes of cough and rhinitis, and increase in size of head. The patient was born out of a consanguineous marriage between first degree relatives, full term, planned LSCS, birth weight 2.4 kg after two female children and two spontaneous abortions prior to this birth each at 3rd month of pregnancy. The baby cried immediately after birth, but 4 hours after birth was shifted to NICU for complaint of regurgitation of feed, tachypnea, excessive secretions at nose and mouth and cough. On examination, patient had complete situs inversus and cleft palate while the investigations revealed left middle lobe collapse consolidation, persistent pulmonary hypertension, hypocalcemia and hypomagnesemia. The patient was treated for pneumonia and respiratory distress and was hospitalized for 70 days, and continued on RT feed till 6 months of age. After 6 months patient developed abnormal body movement, GTCS type, associated with up rolling of eyeballs, secretions from mouth, followed by loss of consciousness. The patient was started on antiepileptic at 6 months of age and is currently on 3 anti-epileptic drugs (Topiramate, Levetiracetam, Vigabatrin). At 8 months of age the complaint of abnormal increase in head size was observed which was progressive till 2 years but beyond that progression slowed down without any medication or treatment. The patient has delayed developmental milestones according to age. The patient was suspected to have Di-George syndrome in view of hypocalcemia, depressed nasal bridge and cleft palate but genetic study FISH for Di-George Syndrome turned out negative for 22q11.2.

On examination the patient was conscious, dull, and revealed mild respiratory distress characterized by tachypnea with mild intercostal retractions, nasal obstruction (due to abundant mucus secretions). Breathing was rhythmic, with a respiratory rate of 50 breaths/minute. The heart rate was normal, 102 beats/minute and SpO₂ 95% on room air and Temp 37.5 °C. Lung percussion was hyper-resonant all over the lung fields. The heart sounds were best heard on the right side of the chest at the sternum, apex beat was felt on right fifth intercostal space along midclavicular line suggestive of dextrocardia. On percussion of abdomen, a tympanitic note was heard, and there was no indication of fluid collection. Nervous system examination revealed large head, DTR +++, equivocal planters with intact sensory system.

Figure 1 :Child had dysmorphic facies with depressed nasal bridge, large head.

Anthropometry of the patient is as follows: Weight 12 kg (between 3rd and 50th percentile), Length 76 cm (below 3rd percentile), Head circumference 50 cm (between 50th and 97th percentile), Mid arm circumference 13.5 cm, and Chest circumference 46 cm.

The current investigations revealed: Blood reports were normal other than finding of Nutritional Anemia with Hb 8.9 gm/dl, MCV 86.2 fl, MCH 27.1 pg, MCHC 26.2 g/dl/TLC-10,800/cumm, DLC- N₇₀ L₂₈ M₁ E₁ B₀ and platelet count 3.60 lakh/cumm. Blood Urea 17 mg/dl, Serum Creatinine 0.81 mg/dl, Serum Uric Acid 4.0 mg/dl, TSH 2.55 uIU, Vitamin D 21 ng/ml, Vitamin B12 30.57 mg/dl. Chest X-ray postero-anterior (PA) view showed cardiac apex and aortic arch on the right side, suggesting dextrocardia. EEG showed intermittent independent spikes, polyspike and slow wave discharges seen from bilateral fronto-central leads with no generalization.

The investigations in newborn period revealed: The newborn screening test on dried blood spot sample was found to be screen negative for congenital hypothyroidism, congenital adrenal hyperplasia, galactosemia, glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency, cystic fibrosis and biotinidase deficiency.

On ultrasonography of abdomen & pelvis, situs inversus was noted with right sided spleen, left sided liver and gall bladder and pancreatic head on left side with right sided pancreatic tail.

2D Echo and Color Doppler revealed dextrocardia with L-looping (Mirror image heart) with other findings normal. A 4 mm patent foramen ovale with left to right shunt was seen.

Multi-Detector Computed Tomography (MDCT) scan chest plain and post contrast showed situs invertus with dextrocardia showing right sided cardiac apex, left sided liver, right sided stomach and spleen (in the visualized cuts) suggestive of situs invertus totalis with dextrocardia. Mirroring of lung anatomy was also noted with trilobed left lung and bilobed right lung (Figure 2).

Figure 2 MDCT scan chest plain and post contrast: showed situs inversus with dextrocardia showing right sided cardiac apex, left sided liver, right sided stomach and spleen (in the visualized cuts) suggestive of situs inversus totalis with dextrocardia. Mirroring of lung anatomy is also noted with trilobed left lung and bilobed right lung. Segmental area of collapse/consolidation seen in lateral segment of left middle lobe with subsegmental collapse also seen in medial segment of left middle lobe. Rest of the lung parenchyma appears normal. No focal parenchymal nodule is seen. There is no septal thickening, sub-plural honeycombing, traction bronchiectasis or areas of ground glass haziness to suggest an interstitial lung disease. The trachea and mainstream bronchi are normal. There is no significant mediastinal or hilar lymphadenopathy. There is no obvious cardiomegaly. Complete mirroring of major neck vessels is noted with right sided aortic arch showing first branch a common trunk giving rise to left subclavian and left common carotid artery followed by right common artery and right subclavian artery. These vessels otherwise appear normal with no other obvious major vascular anomalies visualised. The plural spaces appear normal. Visualised superior aspect of liver appears otherwise normal. Infant feeding tube is seen in situ with gaseous distension of oesophagus.

EEG at 7 months of age showed intermittent epileptogenic focal slow wave disturbance over bilateral parieto-temporo-occipital regions. No generalized paroxysms of epileptiform activity were noted. EEG was suggestive of hypsarrhythmia.

Neuro-sonography suggestive of mild dilatation of lateral and third ventricles with normal caliber of 4th ventricle. Lateral ventricle diameter at the level of 3rd ventricle measured: Right side: 27.2 mm with hemispheric width 59.4 mm, left side: 24.7 mm with hemispheric width 58.9 mm, 3rd ventricle width measured 15.4 mm. The corpus callosum was present above the cavum septum pellucidum. Visualized cisterns & cortical sulci appeared normal. Visualized supra & infratentorial brain parenchyma appeared normal. The cerebellar vermis, fourth ventricle, and cerebellar hemispheres appeared normal. Posterior fossa was sub-optimally visualized however grossly appeared normal.

2D Echo and Color Doppler revealed dextrocardia with L-looping (Mirror image heart) with other findings being normal.

At 9 months, MR scan, 3D arterial spin labelling (non-contrast perfusion), Single voxel spectroscopy and Diffusion Tensor imaging of brain was performed as shown in Figure 3, 4, 5 and 6 respectively.

Figure 3. MR scan reveals: Prominence of CSF spaces along bilateral fronto-temporal convexities. Prominence of both lateral and third ventricles. Near symmetric patchy ill-defined lesions scattered in bilateral periventricular frontoparietal white matter, as seen with periventricular leukomalacia. Hypomyelination. Diffuse thinning of corpus callosum and paucity of bilateral periventricular white matter. Suggestion of pachygyria microgyria pattern along left frontal convexity. No area of restricted diffusion. These findings are suggestive of periventricular leukomalacia with white matter volume loss and associated ex-vacuo dilatation of both lateral and third ventricles. These findings have been described with West syndrome.

Figure 4 : 3D ARTERIAL SPIN LABELLING (NON-CONTRAST PERFUSION) was performed. Cerebral blood flow (CBF) was assessed. Maintained cerebral perfusion was seen.

Figure 5 Single voxel spectroscopy was performed using short TE PRESS sequences (35ms). 2 x 2 x 2 cm sized voxels have been placed in the grey and white matter. The spectra are of good quality with adequate water suppression. NAA, Cho, Cr and ml peaks were identified. No abnormal metabolic peak seen.

Figure 6 DIFFUSION TENSOR IMAGING OF BRAIN was performed using diffusion gradient in 13 directions. Post processing was performed using READY VIEW on ADVANTAGE GE workstation. Fractional anisotropy images with coloured orientation were obtained. Fibre tracking was also performed. *There is diffuse thinning of corpus callosum. There is mild reduction in FA value in periventricular white matter.*

At 1 year of age, Whole Exome sequencing was done which showed gene and transcript *SPAG1* NM_172218.2 with variant c.140G>T (p.Arg47Ile), location Exon 2, homozygous suggestive of Ciliary Dyskinesia, Primary, 28 (615506) with autosomal recessive inheritance.

The patient responded well to increasing the dose of anti-epileptic drug topiramate. Seizures were probably precipitated due to unavailability of vigabatrin, as the drug is not being imported in the COVID-19 pandemic period. Inhaled salbutamol and chest physiotherapy was advised. Vitamin D and B12 supplementation was started. Dietary advice was given for growth faltering.

DISCUSSION

Ciliary motility disorders can be congenital or acquired. Primary Ciliary Dyskinesia (PCD) is a term used to describe congenital ciliary motility disorders. Situs inversus affects about half of all Primary Ciliary Dyskinesia patients. Kartagener's syndrome is a term used to describe PCD with a situs inversus [3]. Because these patients lack mucociliary clearance, recurrent upper and lower respiratory tract infections eventually lead to irreversible lung damage, such as bronchiectasis [4]. The bronchial tree of PCD patients is typically colonised by *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Pseudomonas* species [5].

A clinical picture suggestive of recurrent chest infections, bronchitis, and rhinitis throughout childhood, as well as one or more of the following, are diagnostic criteria for this condition:

1. patient/sibling with situs inversus;
2. spermatozoa that are alive but immotile;
3. decreased or missing transbronchial mucociliary clearance; and
4. cilia with a specific ultrastructural abnormality on electron microscopy [6].

Some PCD patients additionally have hydrocephalus or cerebral ventriculomegaly. The cilia that line the ventricular ependyma of the brain and spinal cord are likely to be dysfunctional in PCD, causing ventricular dilation [7].

The signs and symptoms of primary ciliary dyskinesia vary, but may include: [8, 9]

- Neonatal respiratory distress
- Frequent respiratory infections that can lead to severe lung damage
- Chronic nasal congestion

- Frequent sinus infections
- Recurrent middle ear infections, particularly in early childhood
- Hearing loss
- Hydrocephalus
- Infertility

Two types of tests are used to diagnose PCD: -

1. Screening tests: -
 - a) Measurement of exhaled nasal nitric oxide: which is usually low in PCD [10], and
 - b) Saccharin test: to assess mucociliary function of the nasal epithelium [11].
2. Diagnostic tests: -
 - a) Analysis of ciliary beat pattern and frequency using video recording, and
 - b) Ultrastructural ciliary defect confirmation by electron microscopy [12].

Biopsy of the nasal mucosa can be used to collect samples for these assays in both sexes assessing cilia motility and ultrastructure while in females, laparoscopic biopsies of tubal mucosa can also be taken [13].

We could not perform these tests in our case as parents did not give consent and the diagnosis was primarily clinico-radiological and genetic testing based.

Treatment includes conservative and supportive management with antibiotics, intravenous or oral, intermittent or continuous, and are used to treat upper and lower airway infections. Prophylactic antibiotics may be needed in children to prevent lung disease/bronchiectasis and it should be treated with inhaled bronchodilators, mucolytics, and chest physiotherapy [14]. Vaccination should be done against capsulated organism like *Hemophilus Influenzae* and *pneumococcus*.

Very few cases of Kartagener's syndrome have been reported to occur with seizures [15,16]. Our case had infantile spasms, which are difficult to control seizures.

CONCLUSION

Thus, early diagnosis and management of associated complications of Kartagener's syndrome (KS) not only improves the quality of life but also the prognosis of the patients. Late diagnosis with established bronchiectasis worsens the overall the prognosis and quality of life for the patients. A high degree of suspicion about KS among pediatricians with early diagnosis can improve the overall prognosis for patients with KS.

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Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome in Children (MIS-C)

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ABSTRACT

Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children, a hyperinflammatory syndrome associated with severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV2), is a rare but severe complication in children. There is a paucity of knowledge regarding the management of Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C). This review aims to summate the key clinical presentations and management of MIS-C as per current evidence-based guidelines from the national and international bodies.

INTRODUCTION

Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV2), the causative agent of the covid-19 pandemic has affected millions of lives worldwide [1]. Children are less commonly affected and mostly remain asymptomatic or mildly symptomatic. Among the symptomatic children, 10% - 20% may need hospitalization and among the hospitalized children, intensive care is needed in 1% to 3% of the children with severe illness [2]. In SARS-CoV2 exposed children, a new type of disease entity was reported in April 2020, a clinical syndrome resembling Kawasaki Disease (KD) and toxic shock syndrome which was later termed as Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C) [3]. Another name for MIS-C is Pediatric inflammatory multisystem syndrome temporally associated with SARS-CoV-2 (PIMS-TS) [4]. The estimated incidence of MIS-C is 2/100,000 children which is relatively rare but carries high morbidity and mortality [5].

CASE DEFINITION FOR MULTISYSTEM INFLAMMATORY SYNDROME IN CHILDREN (MIS-C):

World Health Organization (WHO) [6], Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) [7], and Royal College of Pediatrics and Child Health (RCPCH) [8] have given the following case definitions for Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C) as summarized in [TABLE 1].

TABLE 1: MIS-C CASE DEFINITION* [3]

Criteria	WHO	CDC	RCPCH
Age	0–19 years	<21 years	All children (age not defined)
Fever	Fever for ≥3 days	Temperature ≥38.0°C for ≥24 hours or subjective fever for ≥24 hours	Persistent fever (≥38.5°C)
Clinical symptoms	At least two of the following: 1. rash, conjunctivitis, and mucocutaneous inflammation; 2. hypotension or shock; 3. cardiac involvement (presence of myocardial dysfunction, pericarditis, valvulitis, or coronary abnormalities including findings on echocardiogram or elevated levels of troponin/N-terminal pro-B-type natriuretic peptide); 4. coagulopathy; 5. acute gastrointestinal symptoms	Both of the following: 1. severe illness (hospitalized); and 2. ≥2 organ systems involved	Both of the following: 1. single or multi-organ dysfunction; and 2. additional features- abdominal pain, confusion, conjunctivitis, cough, diarrhea, headache, lymphadenopathy, mucous membrane changes, neck swelling, rash, respiratory symptoms, sore throat, swollen hands and feet, syncope, and vomiting.